

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

SAFETY PLAN

Deliverable D1.3

PROJECT NO	101117616
CALL/TOPIC	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02
PROJECT ACRONYM	POSEIDON
PROJECT TITLE	Propulsion Of Ships with E-methanol In favour of the Decarbonisation Of Naval transport
START DATE OF PROJECT	01.09.2023
DURATION	48 months until 31.08.2027

Funded by
the European Union

Work package	WP1 – Project coordination, management and governance
Associated Task	T1.4 – Quality and risk management
Deliverable number and name	D1.3 – Safety Plan
Deliverable due date	31.05.2024
Deliverable lead partner	EIFER
Main author(s)	Julian Dailly (EIFER), Simon Uribe (ICODOS), Clémentine Londero & Pauline Pérez (EDF), Anders Palm (SMA), Dimitris Koutsonikolas & Akrivi Asimakopoulou (CERTH), Carlo Beatrice & Luca Marchitto (STEMS), Emmanuele Lo Re (IFM), German Weisser & Bartosz Rozmyslowicz (WIN GD)
Internal reviewer(s)	Clémentine Londero & Pauline Pérez (EDF)
Version	02
Deliverable completion date	31.05.2024

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

CHANGE CONTROL

DOCUMENT HISTORY

VERSION	DATE	CHANGE HISTORY	AUTHOR(S)	ORGANISATION
01	13.05.2024	First version drafted	Julian Dailly based on inputs from all co-authors	EIFER
	27.05.2024	Revision of 1 st version	Clémentine Londero, Pauline Pérez	EDF
02	31.05.2024	Final version drafted	Julian Daily	EIFER

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The activity of the task 1.4 entitled “Quality and risk management” will oversee quality control and risk management to track deviations and be able to react quickly by implementing appropriate mitigation measures which will be reported in the yearly reports (D1.4, D1.5 and D1.6). The POSEIDON safety plan aims at ensuring maximal safety all along the project (D1.3). This deliverable is drafted at the start of the project, based on inputs from partners performing experimental activities (ICODOS, EDF, CERTH, STEMS, IFM, SMA). This living document will serve as a reference for all partners and contribute to establish a safety-culture among all partners. Safer research, design, and operation will contribute to the continuing future of renewable alternative fuels.

AUTHORS’ NOTE

This deliverable is based on the report “Safety Planning and Management in Hydrogen and Fuel Cells Projects – Guidance Document” from the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking¹.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

¹https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/get-involved/european-hydrogen-safety-panel-0/reference-documents_en

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1 INTRODUCTION

The experimental activities of the POSEIDON project aim at designing, manufacturing and testing a conversion unit for the synthesis of e-methanol. The produced e-methanol will be tested in dedicated engines test benches and laboratory facilities. In addition, CO₂-capture experiments will be performed in lab-environment.

The use of hydrogen, methanol, CO₂, under various temperature and pressure operation conditions requires to carefully prepare the work to ensure safe operation. This document presents the basic safety concept, summarizing all necessary aspects and levels to be considered during the project at the various locations where POSEIDON' experiments will be performed. At the present stage, the document cannot be fully completed and will be actualized along the project.

2 PROJECT BRIEF

2.1 GENERAL INFORMATION

The POSEIDON project started on 01.01.2023 and will last until 31.08.2027 (4 years). The project has received funding from the European Union Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement No. 101117616. The project is coordinated by Dr. Julian Dailly from the European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER).

2.2 CONSORTIUM

The POSEIDON consortium consists of a total of 19 partners from 7 countries including:

- 8 industrial partners: EDF, ICODOS, Fincantieri, Isotta Fraschini Motori – IFM, Winterthuer Gas & Diesel – WIN GD, Global Omnium – GOMSL, CAO Hellas,
- 5 research organisations: EIFER, KIT, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki – AUTH, CERTH, CNR-STEMS,
- 2 ports: Fundacion Valenciaport, Port of Thessaloniki – ThPA,
- 2 business support organisations: RINA, Steinbeis Innovation GmbH,
- 1 biomass association: AVEBIOM,
- 1 public agency: Swedish Maritime Association – SMA.

All partners are fully committed to accelerate the transition towards renewable fuels in EU shipping.

2.3 TYPE OF WORK AND LOCATIONS

The experimental activities in POSEIDON will be performed in different locations:

- Mannheim, Germany, ICODOS:

The different modules of the plant will be assembled in the industrial hall of ICODOS in Germany. The construction will take place stepwise as the ordered components are being delivered and they are placed and fixed within the modules. Once the components are assembled in the modules the piping work will start in order to make all the mechanical connections. The modules are assembled separately and then connected for the cold testing. Once the individual components are checked a pressure test will be performed in order to ensure the leak tightness of all the connections. These checks and pressure test will constitute the factory acceptance test (FAT). Once the FAT is completed, the modules will be prepared for transport by disassembling the connecting pipes and electrical connection between modules. Finally, the plant is transported to Les Renardières.

- Paris, France, EDF:

1) The adaptation of the Power to X test platform in Les Renardières to integrate the ICODOS plant (footprint, power, type of valves and connections etc.) will be performed based on the information transmitted by ICODOS on the modular plant. EDF with subcontractor (engineering design office) will carry out studies and plans, in particular to integrate methane supply (which will be needed for the simulation of biogas), storage and filtration which is specific to the ICODOS technology because methane represents approximately 60% of the inlet gas mixture. Also, it will be necessary to design the connector needed between the Power to X test platform and the e-methanol synthesis plant (i.e.: pipe, fitting, valves...), resulting in a complete piping and instrumentation diagram. A risk analysis and a security plan will be carried out by EDF and an external auditor and the adaptation of the Power to X test platform will be conducted by a specialized company and monitored by EDF.

2) The integration and commissioning of the ICODOS technology in the Power to X test platform will be done stepwise. After transportation of all the bricks of the e-methanol demonstrator to the platform, they will be unloaded on the platform with a crane and connected to the various utilities and gas storages which will be used as feedstock for the modular plant. A safety audit will then be carried out in order to make sure that the commissioning and the future operation of the plant can be done without safety issues. Then EDF and ICODOS will bring the different parts of the plant in operation stepwise with neutral gases (N₂, CO₂) and then with real gas mixtures (CH₄, CO₂, H₂S...).

3) Tests on the ICODOS demonstrator will be performed to determine its performance in different working conditions: origin/quality of CO₂ (wastewater treatment plant, lime plant, etc.), flexibility/partial load operation, sensitivity to some pollutants, etc.

- Winterthur, Switzerland, WIN GD:

WinGD will conduct experiments on its Spray Combustion Chamber (SCC – e-methanol needs about 10 kg), to examine its fundamental combustion characteristics. The compatibility of the e-methanol with the engines fuel system will be assessed thanks to a dedicated test rig (e-methanol needs about 2 t). These tests will be run for a few hundred thousand cycles, in order to allow projections for typical lifetime of WinGD's systems. Furthermore, WinGD's single cylinder engine will be upgraded to feature a e-methanol injection system and used to test the produced e-fuel (e-methanol needs about 20 t) and characterize the engine performances including emissions. A wide range of pollutants will be measured, including NO_x, SO_x, CO, formaldehyde, complete HC speciation (with FTIR) and carbon black. A detailed characterization of particles (mass, number, size distribution) will be also

conducted and compared with conventional fuel operation. On the GHG side, CO₂, methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) will be considered.

- Napoli, Italy, STEMS / IFM

IFM and STEMS will perform tests on a 4-stroke single-cylinder engine in its Dual-Fuel MeOH-Diesel version for about 100 hours (e-methanol needs 2 t). These tests aim at evaluating the engine performances, the environmental impacts as well as the condition of the engine components after e-methanol use. The latter will address any engine durability requirements that need to be fulfilled with the produced e-fuel. Like for the 2-Stroke engine, exhausted pollutants as gaseous and solid particles will be measured.

- Norrköping, Sweden, SMA

A demonstration of the use of the produced e-methanol in real conditions will be done on SMA's pilot boat (retrofit of this pilot boat from diesel to methanol done in the EU funded FASTWATER project) (e-methanol need 1 500L).

- Thessaloniki, Greece, CERTH

CERTH will perform work on innovative CO₂ capture technologies. Synthetic gas mixtures with CO₂ content from < 5 – 40 vol% and integrating main impurities/pollutants (e.g. NO_x, SO_x, H₂S) will be treated in a Membrane Gas Absorption (MGA) unit.

All the safety aspects will be presented in the section 3 and divided per experimental sites.

2.4 SAFETY RESPONSIBLE PERSON

The experimental activities being performed in different locations, it is necessary to define a safety responsible person for each site:

- Jens Geppert: Mannheim, Germany, ICODOS
- Pauline Perez: Paris, France, EDF
- Stephen Okere: Winterthur, Switzerland, WINGD
- Renata Tremaroli: CNR safety officer, Giuseppe Perretta, local contact for Napoli, Italy, STEMS
- Albert Hagander: Norrköping, Sweden, SMA
- Dimitris Koutsonikolas: Thessaloniki, Greece, CERTH

3 PROJECT SAFETY PER SITE

3.1 MANNHEIM, GERMANY, ICODOS

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1.	Project Brief		
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EIFER, EDF, KIT , RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS , FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH, STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Jens Geppert COO & Co-Founder, ICODOS GmbH Tel +49 15679 1551 03 / jens.geppert@icodos.com
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

1e.	Description of Work	Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract)	Development, construction and commissioning of a modular plant as a demonstrator based on ICODOS's innovative hybrid CO ₂ -capture and e-methanol synthesis technology.
1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning of the project: Basic and Detail Engineering • Executing a HAZOP analysis or risk assessment • Procurement of Equipment for the modular plant • Pre-assembling of the modular plant • Transport to the site of erection (EDF, France) • Construction and assembling • Commissioning
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No storage of hydrogen in ICODOS scope. The hydrogen is provided by EDF and use as feedstock for methanol.
1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure 3000 kg <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Temporary storage in buffer tank. The final storage of the methanol product is in EDF scope

- 1h. Location Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)
- Specially controlled area
 - Industrial environment
 - Research lab
 - Public
 - Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.:

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC PED 2014/68/EU, EN-standards, AD 2000 HP 100 R ATEX, IEC, EN-Standards ISO, IEC	Jens Geppert
2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	Planned: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HAZID • HAZOP • Explosion protection document • Fire and Gas protection document Estimated date August 2024	Jens Geppert

2c.	Prevention mitigation and	List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...). Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)	Planned: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of changes/results of the HAZOP in the planning e.g. P&ID →proper design • Creation of standard operational procedures to mitigate the risks associated with the construction, commissioning, operation and maintenance of the plant • Training of operating personnel • Calibration of safety related devices 	Jens Geppert
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N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	See document: 20231115_Draft Report on Critical process parameters on the POSEIDON Sharepoint	Jens Geppert
3b.	Procedures for operation	Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	A document called Functional Design Specification with all procedures for operation is being finished. Based on this document an operation manual specially design for the operators is to be developed. Estimated date November 2024	Jens Geppert

3c.	Emergency evacuation and response plans	alarm, and	(maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	A document called Alarm and Trip list is being developed and will cover this point together with an evacuation and response plan developed by EDF with ICODOS supporting Estimated date November 2024	Jens Geppert
3d.	Personnel education and training	education	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	A complete operation manual and the complete as build documentation will be handover to the operator EDF. Additionally, the EDF personnel will be trained by ICODOS for operating the plant. Estimated date February 2026	Jens Geppert
3e.	Monitoring and Periodic Reviews	Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	Constant communication between operator EDF and plant manufacturer ICODOS takes place during regular meetings. ICODOS is during the first months of operation heavily involve ensuring a smooth transition	Jens Geppert	
3f.	Reporting of safety events and lessons learned in HELLEN and HIAD	Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	All the safety events will be recorded and documented to prevent future events in the POSEIDON plant but also in future commercial plants.	Jens Geppert	

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	ATEX zones	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Process chemistry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	Material of construction	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	Material data safety sheets	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	Material and energy balances	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	Electrical classification	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Internal server of ICODOS
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.2 PARIS, FRANCE, EDF

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1. Project Brief			
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EDF, KIT, RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS, FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH, STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Pauline Perez, project manager, EDF R&D (EDF Lab Les Renardières) pauline.perez@edf.fr // +33 7 60 85 98 02
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

- | | | |
|-------------------------|--|--|
| 1e. Description of Work | Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract) | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• <u>Preparation and adaptation of EDF's test facility:</u><ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Studies and plans will be carried out by EDF and engineering design office to integrate methane supply (needed for biogas simulation) and filtration, to design all the connectors needed between ICODOS' plant and the EDF's platform and to adapt the testing area where the technology will be implemented. A risk analysis and a security plan will be carried out by EDF and an external auditor. Then, the adaptation of the Power to X test platform will be conducted by a specialized company and monitored by EDF.• <u>Technology demonstration at EDF Lab Les Renardières:</u><ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Integration and commissioning phase: first assembly of the methanol plant and connection to EDF's test facility. Then EDF and ICODOS will bring the different parts of the plant in operation stepwise with neutral gases (N₂, CO₂) and then with real gas mixtures (CH₄, CO₂, H₂S...).2. Test campaigns phase: carry out the tests defined beforehand during the project in order to determine the plant's performance in different working conditions: origin/quality of CO₂, flexibility/partial load operation, sensitivity to some pollutants, etc.▪ Two main campaigns will be carried out:<ul style="list-style-type: none">- production of a defined quantity of methanol (~25 tons) under nominal conditions- operation in stressful conditions (partial loads, addition of pollutants...) |
|-------------------------|--|--|

1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation and adaptation of EDF’s test facility: first semester of 2025 • Integration and commissioning phase: September 2025 to February 2026 (M25-M30) • Test campaigns phase: March 2026 to August 2026 (M31-M36)
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory at EDF Lab Les Renardières	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar 810 kg <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar 160 kg <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): kg
1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure 28 000 kg
1h.	Location	Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specially controlled area <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial environment <input type="checkbox"/> Research lab <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.: high-voltage power lines, other R&D labs at the Les Renardières site (ex: power lines)

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EDF Lab Les Renardières site is subject by ICPE legislation regarding French environmental code, on the declaration specification (4715 for presence of hydrogen, 1434 for distribution of combustible substances). The site must comply with the provisions of its local decree dated 18 July 2011 and referenced "AP n°11 DRIEE 106 AP n°11 DRIEE 106 imposant des prescriptions spéciales à la société EDF pour son centre de recherche des Renardières à Ecuelles" (imposing special requirements on EDF for its Les Renardières research centre in Ecuelles). The site is also subject to IOTA regulations concerning the abstraction and discharge of water into the river Seine. <p>EDF's engineering design office will soon provide the standards policies (beginning of June).</p>	Adeline Leblanc
2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	<p>A preliminary hazard study is ongoing and carried out by INERIS (public expert in technological risk management) to model accident scenarios for EDF's test facilities (results by June).</p> <p>Hazard study carried out by EDF's risk assessment engineer (second semester of 2024).</p> <p>Preliminary HAZOP of EDF's test facility conducted by EDF's engineering design office (May-June 2024).</p> <p>HAZOP study of EDF's test facility integrating ICODOS' HAZOP (around July 2024).</p>	Adeline Leblanc

Main identified industrial risks:

- Bursting of a hydrogen tube trailer caught in a fire
- Flash fire caused by a H₂ pipe rupture
- Bursting of the methanol tank caught in a fire
- Internal bursting of the methanol tank

2c.	Prevention and mitigation	List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...). Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)	Fire protection on EDF's facility: fire hydrant planned Gas detection: hydrogen, H ₂ S, SO ₂ Physical protection of H ₂ pipes Demonstration phase: some test campaigns will require the addition of toxic and hazardous pollutants (H ₂ S and SO ₂), they will not be stored pure but mixed with nitrogen.	Adeline Leblanc
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Prevention and mitigation of EDF's facility will be precised by June.

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	Pressure monitoring for gas storages, pipes, liquid storages (CO ₂ , N ₂ , methanol, liquid effluents). Level monitoring on liquid storages. Temperature monitoring in ICODOS plant. Nominal and limit values to be defined during detailed design.	Pauline Perez

3b.	Procedures for operation	Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	Procedure for operation will be created during the project by ICODOS and EDF (end of 2024 and beg. of 2025).	Pauline Perez
3c.	Emergency alarm, evacuation and response plans	(maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	Emergency alarms are directly connected to the guard post of EDF Lab Les Renardières site which will contact the rescue services and secure the area. This part will be precised later (end of 2024 and beg. of 2025).	Pauline Perez
3d.	Personnel education and training	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	EDF test facility's staff for supervising and civil works Operation staff (people from EDF and ICODOS) ICODOS staff for assembly and commissioning Each actor will be trained and qualified according to its activities (electrical, chemical risks, mechanical authorizations, etc.) This will be documented later in the project (2025).	Pauline Perez
3e.	Monitoring and Periodic Reviews	Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	Live monitoring is planned for the demonstration plant. Will be detailed later (end of 2024 and beg. of 2025).	Pauline Perez
3f.	Reporting of safety events and lessons learned in HELLEN and HIAD	Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	Feedback on safety events will be continuously followed during the project. Safety events that might occur on EDF's test facility will be reported to feed the lessons learned databases.	Pauline Perez

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	POSEIDON Sharepoint: 2024_02_22_PFD.pdf
	ATEX zones	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Process chemistry	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material of construction	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material data safety sheets	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material and energy balances	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	POSEIDON Sharepoint: 2024_02_22_Mass Balance.pdf
	Electrical classification	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.3 WINTHERTUR, SWITZERLAND, WINGD

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1. Project Brief			
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EDF, KIT , RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS , FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH, STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Stephen Okere, Environment, Health, Safety (EHS) & Facility Manager Stephen.okere@wingd.com
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

1e.	Description of Work	Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract)	<p>Year 2 of the project: Planning and preparation for test facilities for the test, which might include design engineering work and ordering and manufacturing of components needed for tests.</p> <p>After reception of the e-methanol (M33; M#8), a first set of experiments will be conducted on WinGD’s Spray Combustion Chamber (SCC – e-methanol needs about 10 kg), in order to examine its fundamental combustion characteristics. The compatibility of the e-methanol with the engines fuel system will be assessed thanks to a dedicated test rig (e-methanol needs about 2 t). These tests will be run for a few hundred thousand cycles, in order to allow projections for typical lifetime of WinGD’s systems. Furthermore, WinGD’s single cylinder engine will be upgraded to feature an e-methanol injection system (D4.5) and used to test the produced e-fuel (e-methanol needs about 20 t) and characterize the engine performances including emissions (WinGD, AUTH).</p>														
1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	<p>Year 2025 / project year 2 – planning, preparation of tests, engineering design work and manufacturing if needed</p> <p>Year 2026 / project year 3 – testing phase of received methanol, installation of components and modification of test facilities if needed</p>														
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<table border="0"> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic)</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride)</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC):</td> <td>..... kg</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg	<input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg	<input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): kg
<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg																
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): kg																

1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure	47 500 kg
1h.	Location	Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Specially controlled area <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Industrial environment <input type="checkbox"/> Research lab <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.: Fossil fuels, compressed gasses, NH ₃ , lubricating oils.	

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	Legal Basis <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Federal Act on Work in Industry, Trade and Commerce (Arbeitsgesetz, ArG), SR 822.11 - Ordinances to the Arbeitsgesetz - Federal Law on Accident Insurance (UVG), SR 832.20 - Ordinances to the Accident Insurance Act Further regulations EKAS / Suva (Work safety and health protection) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EKAS 1825, Directive Flammable liquids - EKAS 6507, Guideline Ammonia, storage and handling - EKAS 6517, Directive on liquefied petroleum gas - Suva 2153, Explosion protection principles, minimum requirements, zones 	Stephen Okere

VKF (Fire protection)

- Fire safety regulations VKF

Kantone (Environmental protection)

- Storage of hazardous substances, practical guide
- Protection and drainage of goods handling areas

2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere
2c.	Prevention and mitigation	List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...). Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere
3b.	Procedures for operation	Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere
3c.	Emergency evacuation and response plans	alarm, and (maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	In progress	Stephen Okere
3d.	Personnel education and training	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	In progress	Stephen Okere
3e.	Monitoring and Periodic Reviews	Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere
3f.	Reporting of safety events/lessons learned in HELLEN/HIAD	Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)	Stephen Okere

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)
	ATEX zones	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	In preparation (to be filled in 2024)
	Process chemistry	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material of construction	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material data safety sheets	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material and energy balances	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Electrical classification	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.4 NAPOLI, ITALY, STEMS / IFM

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1. Project Brief			
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EDF, KIT, RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS, FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH, STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Renata Tremaroli, CNR national safety manager, email: renata.tremaroli@cnr.it ; phone: +390649937624 Giuseppe Perretta STEMS safety manager, email: giuseppe.perretta@stems.cnr.it ; phone: +390817177167
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

1e.	Description of Work	Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract)	STEMS will perform tests on a 4-stroke single-cylinder engine in its Dual-Fuel MeOH-Diesel version for about 100 hours (e-methanol needs 2 t). These tests aim at evaluating the engine performance, the environmental impacts as well as the condition of the engine components after e-methanol use.
1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	Preparation of STEMS SCE lab for methanol tests: first semester of 2025. Test campaigns phase of SCE in Dual-fuel methanol-diesel version: June 2026 to November 2026 (M32-M39).
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): kg
1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure 1000 kg
1h.	Location	Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specially controlled area <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial environment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research lab <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.:

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	STEMS engine cell lab design and operation guidelines for safe methanol tests will refer to IGF code for safety & design guidelines (https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Safety/Pages/IGF-Code.aspx).	Luca Marchitto
2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	<p>A preliminary hazard study about the storage and use of Methanol is ongoing in parallel to the design of the plant.</p> <p>To this aim, a specialized Italian Company (SPF srl) in design, provision, installation and certification of hazard supply liquid and gas fuel systems has been engaged.</p> <p>Main identified industrial risks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bursting of the methanol tank caught in a fire • Internal bursting of the methanol tank <p>Complete details on the methanol storage and supply line, main safety devices, safety equipment and safety procedures for engine tests with methanol will be released in October 2024.</p>	Luca Marchitto
2c.	Prevention and mitigation	<p>List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...).</p> <p>Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)</p>	<p>Fire protection on STEMS's facility:</p> <p>Vapour detection: Methanol.</p> <p>Prevention and mitigation of fire in STEMS's facility will be released by October 2024.</p>	Luca Marchitto

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	<p>Pressure monitoring for gas storages, pipes, liquid storages (CO₂, N₂, methanol, liquid effluents).</p> <p>Level monitoring on methanol storages.</p> <p>Temperature monitoring in the methanol tank and in the supply line from tank to the engine.</p> <p>Nominal and limit values to be defined during detailed design.</p>	Luca Marchitto
3b.	Procedures operation	for Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	<p>Before engine starting, functional checks are performed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check for any oil, water, and exhaust gas leakages. - Preliminary check with the engine running. <p>The aforementioned operations will be carried out with the engine off/idle and with the PPE provided for maximum level of exposure as reported in the Annex 4.1.</p> <p>Once the functional checks have been completed, the engine tests are carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engine startup; - System parameters setting from the control panel; - Engine test acquisitions and monitoring. <p>During phases where the engine has a speed higher than idle, access to engine room is prohibited, and the doors must be closed.</p>	Luca Marchitto

3c.	Emergency evacuation and response plans	alarm, and	(maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	Emergency alarm, evacuation and response plans in case of fire in STEMS's facility will be released in October 2024.	Luca Marchitto
3d.	Personnel and training	education	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	Education and training procedures of the personnel involved in methanol engine tests at STEMS's facility will be released in October 2024.	Luca Marchitto
3e.	Monitoring and Periodic Reviews		Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	Monitoring and periodic checks of the plant and safety devices will be released after the methanol storage and supply line system. It is expected in October 2024.	Luca Marchitto
3f.	Reporting of safety events/lessons learned in HELLEN/HIAD		Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	POSEIDON partners involved in engine tests can organize dedicated meeting to present, share and review safety systems and procedures to uniform their laboratories.	Luca Marchitto

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ATEX zones	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Process chemistry	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material of construction	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material data safety sheets	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Located on the internal STEMS server
	Material and energy balances	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Electrical classification	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Located on the internal STEMS server
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	D1.3 Safety Plan, Annex 4.1.; Located on the internal STEMS server
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.5 NORRKÖPING, SWEDEN, SMA

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1. Project Brief			
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EDF, KIT, RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS, FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH, STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Albert Hagander, technical director albert.hagander@sjofartsverket.se , Tel: +46104784722
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
1e.	Description of Work	Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract)	Demonstration runs of a Swedish Maritime Administration pilot boat with a current methanol engine on e-methanol produced in the POSEIDON project.

1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	Testing of the project produced fuel in the late part of the project, demonstration phase.
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC): kg
1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure Onboard pilot boat 1450 Liter MD97 bunkering station 7300 Liter
1h.	Location	Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Specially controlled area <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial environment <input type="checkbox"/> Research lab <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.: Co-located with lubricants.

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	<p>The vessel is not an IMO nor Class vessel but follows Swedish national rule (TSFS 2017:25, Swedish Transport Agency's Code of Statute).</p> <p>The boat is built in accordance with the Swedish Maritime Administration's Service Regulation 2/97, with the approval of the Swedish Maritime Administration.</p> <p>High voltage regulations ELSÄK-FS 1995:5, issued by the Swedish Electrical Safety Authority.</p> <p>EMC, Electromagnetic Compatibility (89/336/EEC with amendments 92/31/EEC and 3/68/EEC)</p> <p>LVD, Low Voltage Equipment (73/23/EEC with amendments 93/68/EEC)</p> <p>Machinery (89/392/EEC with amendments)</p> <p>Hydraulics (SS-EN 982)</p> <p>The boat is designed and built in a professional manner and in such a way that future service, maintenance and repairs are facilitated.</p>	Albert Hagander
2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	<p>A risk assessment has been performed and it considers the design and operation of the methanol system onboard the pilot boat.</p> <p>See Annex 4.2</p>	Albert Hagander

2c.	Prevention and mitigation	List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...). Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander
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N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander
3b.	Procedures for operation	Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander
3c.	Emergency alarm, evacuation and response plans	(maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander

3d. Personnel education and training	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander
3e. Monitoring and Periodic Reviews	Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	See Annex 4.2	Albert Hagander
3f. Reporting of safety events and lessons learned in HELLEN and HIAD	Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	Not relevant	Albert Hagander

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ATEX zones	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Process chemistry	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material of construction	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material data safety sheets	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material and energy balances	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Electrical classification	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3.6 THESSALONIKI, GREECE, CERTH

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input
1. Project Brief			
1a.	General Information	Title of project:	POSEIDON; Project number 101117616
		Term (duration):	09/2023 to 08/2027
		Funding:	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-02-08
		Coordinator (Person, Institution):	Dr. Julian Dailly, European Institute for Energy Research (EIFER)
1b.	Consortium	List of partners (those with hydrogen safety specific experience are highlighted)	EDF, KIT , RINA, FVP, AUTH, ICODOS , FINCANTIERI, IFM, Steinbeis, GOMSL, ThPA, CERTH , STEMS, SMA, INV, CAO HELLAS, AVEBIOM, WIN GD
1c.	Safety Responsible Person	Name and contact data of person responsible for safety of the site “safety officer”	Dr. Dimitrios Koutsonikolas, Tel: +30 2310.498.250 Mob: +30 6948047875 Mail : dkoutson@certh.gr
1d.	Type of Work	Describe the specific nature of the work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Laboratory-scale research <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bench-scale testing <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering development <input type="checkbox"/> Safety engineering <input type="checkbox"/> Prototype operation <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Commercial application <input type="checkbox"/> Other:

1e.	Description of Work	Short summary of the Description of Activities (maybe copy of the short summary of the contract)	Experimental tests of CO ₂ capture in a bench scale Membrane Gas Absorption (MGA) unit, using synthetic gas mixtures and liquid solvents (e.g. methanol and DEA).
1f.	Project Phases (origin of change)	What is done in which phase of the project	Experimental tests and process assessment, M6-M20.
1g1.	Hydrogen Inventory	Type of hydrogen storage and maximum inventory of hydrogen physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input type="checkbox"/> p < 2 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p < 20 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p <= 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> p > 200 bar kg <input type="checkbox"/> Liquid (cryogenic) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Solid storage (metal hydride) kg <input type="checkbox"/> Other (e.g. LOHC):
1g2.	Methanol Inventory	Type of methanol storage and maximum inventory of methanol physically stored on site(s) per storage type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Liquid, atmospheric pressure ~20 kg
1h.	Location	Where is your activity, respectively hydrogen / methanol located (industrial, public, colocation with other technologies and hazards, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Specially controlled area <input type="checkbox"/> Industrial environment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research lab <input type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Co-located with other hazardous materials, fuels, etc.:

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not "safety officer"
2. Project safety				
2a.	Relevant regulations, codes, standards and safety policies	List of relevant regulation and applied codes and standards for your projects	State regulation; CERTH Health and Safety Internal Procedure; MSDS	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
2b.	Hazard Identification and Risk Assessment	Provide a chronological list of hazard identification procedures and risk assessments done (or planned) and summarize key results or provide full documentation in attachments	Template for new lab scale units from CERTH Health and Safety Internal Procedure (completed in Greek);	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
2c.	Prevention and mitigation	List all prevention strategies and installed mitigation technology used (e.g. ventilation, water sprays, sensors, ...). Follow the first 8 safety principles, (potential outcome of 2b.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storage • Ventilation • Cool room and storehouses with temperature monitoring • Regular wastes' disposal (usually before summertime) • Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) 	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas

N°	Topic	Explanation	Input	Responsible, if not “safety officer”
3. Operations Management				
3a.	Nominal and limit values of critical process parameters	Provide a list of controlled or easy to check process parameters, like filling status of a liquid, pressure and or temperature and corresponding design and limit values (potential outcome of 2b.)	Not relevant	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
3b.	Procedures for operation	Refer to checklists for start or/ and shut-down, operation instructions (potential outcome of 2b and possibly attached in 4)	Not relevant	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
3c.	Emergency alarm, evacuation and response plans	(maybe just attach them in 4 and indicate this here)	CERTH Emergency plan (incl. fire incidents)	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
3d.	Personnel education and training	Describe or list all measures where involved persons (operators, first responders, ...) are participating in courses and explain how this is documented	Basic training on health and safety upon recruitment of CERTH employees. Regular evacuation drills (i.e. twice a year)	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
3e.	Monitoring and Periodic Reviews	Describe the procedures and periodicity of checking whether everything above is in place and known by all relevant people	CERTH Technical Unit checks regularly all installed fire extinguishing systems	CERTH level: Safety technical manager Project level: D. Koutsonikolas
3f.	Reporting of safety events and lessons learned in HELLEN/HIAD	Describe plans for sharing safety critical information	Not relevant	

N°	Topic	Available?	Where (Link, Library, Room, ...)
4.	Checklists and other helpful documents (for EHSP highly relevant documents in bold font)		
	Block flow diagram (PID) or simplified process flow diagram	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	ATEX zones	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Process chemistry	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material of construction	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material data safety sheets	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Material and energy balances	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Electrical classification	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Pressure relief system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Ventilations system design	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Technical documentation of further safety / mitigation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Checklists before or after start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV before or at project start	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before hardware installation	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Results of ISV or risk assessment before operations	<input type="checkbox"/>	

4 ANNEX

4.1 STEMS/IFM: PERSONAL PROTECTIVE EQUIPMENT (PPE) / TEST PROCEDURES

The human body can be exposed to methanol through inhalation, ingestion, or skin contact. Respiratory protection is mandatory to prevent methanol intake via inhalation. Different levels of respiratory protection may be required depending on the concentration of methanol in the atmosphere. Respiratory protection is not necessary if the methanol concentration is <200 ppm. However, if it exceeds 200 ppm for an extended period, respiratory protection is essential, along with protection to prevent further exposure routes like ingestion, eye, and skin contact. If the sustained methanol concentration is higher than 200 ppm, a self-contained breathing apparatus (SCBA) is necessary. Additionally, wearing safety goggles with side shields, gloves, and an apron is necessary. When handling methanol, it is essential to wear chemical-resistant clothing to avoid skin exposure. Materials like butyl rubber and nitrile rubber are suitable for this purpose [1]. A list of PPE based on risk level is reported in table 3 [2].

Table 3: Personal Protective Equipment selection as function of risk level.

Level of exposure	Personal Protective Equipment
Low risk of vapour/low risk of volume splash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fire retardant clothing • Gloves (disposable nitrile) • Safety glasses with side shields • Full boot cover
High risk of vapour/low risk of volume splash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full chemical resistant suite • Chemical resistant rubber gloves • Full face supplied air respirator • Chemical resistant anti-static rubber boots
High risk of vapour/High risk of volume splash	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full chemical resistant impermeable suite • Chemical resistant rubber gloves • SCBA/Compressed air breathing apparatus (CABA) • Chemical resistant anti-static rubber boots

Before engine starting, functional checks are performed:

- Check for any oil, water, and exhaust gas leaks;
- Devices calibration forbidden with the engine on;
- Preliminary check with the engine running.

The aforementioned operations must be carried out with the engine off/idle and with the PPE provided for maximum level of exposure as reported in the table 3.

Once the functional checks have been completed, the engine tests are carried out:

- Engine startup;
- System parameters setting from the control panel;
- Engine test acquisitions and monitoring.

During phases where the engine has a speed higher than idle, access to engine room is prohibited, and the doors must be closed.

4.2 SMA: RISK ASSESSMENT WORKSHEET

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
Methanol Storage & Supply Systems	What if the ship is involved in a collision event? (Ship or Infrastructure)	Ship involved in a collision event	Damage to the tank resulting in a methanol leak and create toxic atmosphere.	The tank is located on the centreline of the vessel. -Side shell to tank 1800mm	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
			Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	In the event of a significant collision the tank room would be flooded and therefore dilute any methanol release.	B - Ex. Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low			
		Damage to the methanol tank vent system	Tank is not protected by flame arrestor.	The location of the vent is close to the cabin, and therefore expected to have some protection from the side rails and other structure	C - Very Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low	1. The tank vent should be away from the side and not bouncing into other vessel.		ScandINAOS / Simrishamn
What if the ship is involved in a grounding event? What if the space floods? What if the ship sinks?	Ship involved in a grounding event	Flooding in the outer tank	Methanol leak in the tank room and increase risk of a fire event.	In the event of a significant collision the tank room would be flooded and therefore dilute any methanol release.	C - Very Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low			
			It was considered that the shorting of the electrical systems would result in the closure of the solenoid valves (FTC)	- Shutdown methanol system - El. Equipment are Ex-class	A - Remote	1 - Minor	Low			
			There could be a small methanol release to the sea through the vent line	Methanol is not considered a significant risk to marine or aquatic life	A - Remote	1 - Minor	Low			
			Ship sinking	Methanol release to sea	Methanol is not considered a significant risk to marine or aquatic life	A - Remote	1 - Minor	Low		
What if the addition of the tank impacted vessel structure / stability? What if the tank supports were inadequate?	The additional weight and location of it onboard could impact the ships stability	Inadequate support for the additional systems	The ship could be at an increased risk of capsizing	Negligible impact on the ships stability, due to the location of the equipment. Stability assessment shall be completed.				2. Stability assessment should be completed.	SMA to provide stability booklet.	ScandINAOS
			There could be structural damage to the ship	Structural assessment to be completed				3. Structural assessment to be completed.		ScandINAOS
			The systems could be damaged if inadequately supported, resulting in an increased risk of leak.	Structural assessment to be completed						
			Connection of the inner and outer tank	If there is any differential movement between the	The tank shall be designed and fabricated in accordance following					
			inner and outer tanks there could be damage to the methanol piping system. An undetected failure of the outer tank, resulting in a methanol release to the tank room.	quality assurance and quality control processes.						
			A methanol leak to the outer tank and create toxic atmosphere.	- There shall be a vapour detector installed at a location adjacent to the outlet of the ventilation inside the tank - There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures. - Crew is not expected to be present near outer tank except during maintenance.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
			A methanol leak to the outer tank would result in an increased risk of a fire event.	- The outer tank is designed to sustain the leakage. - There shall be a vapour detector installed at a location adjacent to the outlet of the ventilation inside the tank- All equipment within the space shall be of a suitable EX rated- There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures.	B - Ex. Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low			

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	What if there is an external impact (lifting operations / external damage)?	Damage to the tank, due to external impact / dropped object. No credible case identified, as it is not possible to lift any large items above it due to restricted head-height.								
		Damage to the piping system in the tank room, with no credible risks identified as it is routed alongside the tank and persons only access is to crawl along the adjacent walkway.								
		Damage to the piping system in the engine room, with no credible risks identified due to its routing, which has been kept short and runs alongside the engine.								
What if there is an adjacent / external fire / explosion event? (at sea / alongside)	A fire event in the tank room	The methanol storage tank and associated piping systems could be exposed to higher temperatures, resulting in an increased risk of leakage, with methanol contributing to the fuel of the fire.	There is heat fire alarm in outer tank. Tank room is considered low fire risk. Manual fire suppression system which also can cool down the methanol tank.	B - Ex. Unlikely	3 - Major	Medium				
	Fire in the engine room	The methanol storage tank and associated piping systems could be exposed to higher temperatures, resulting in an increased risk of leakage, with methanol contributing to the fuel of the fire.	- A-60 insulation along engine room bulkhead. - There should be a fire suppression system in the engine room.	B - Ex. Unlikely	3 - Major	Medium				

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
			A methanol leak to the engine room due to pipe damage	- Fire alarm in engine room will automatically close the master valve of fuel supply system. - There should be chemical powder fire extinguisher in the engine room. - The master valve should be shutoff and the methanol supply is cut off	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
	What if there was an internal fire in the outer tank	A fire in the outer tank	The methanol storage tank and associated piping systems could be exposed to higher temperatures, resulting in an increased risk of leakage, with methanol contributing to the fuel of the fire.	- There shall be a vapour detector installed at a location adjacent to the outlet of the ventilation inside the tank- All equipment within the space shall be of a suitable EX rated- There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures.	A - Remote	3 - Major	Low			
	What if there are equipment failures? - Liquid / vapour leak from storage tank - Liquid / vapour leak from tank connections - Liquid / vapour leak in the outer tank - What if there is a valve leak / passing valve	Leak from a threaded connection within the outer tank	Leakage resulting in a toxic atmosphere.	- There shall be a vapour detector installed at a location adjacent to the outlet of the ventilation inside the tank - There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures. - Crew is not expected to be present near outer tank except during maintenance.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	- What if there are corrosion / damage mechanisms - What if there are manufacturing defects - What are the probable maximum leakage cases?		Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	- There shall be a vapour detector installed at a location adjacent to the outlet of the ventilation inside the tank - All equipment within the space shall be of a suitable EX rated - There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
		Leak from a connection to the engine in the engine room	leakage result in a create toxic atmosphere.	- There shall be vapour detectors installed in the engine room - The methanol supply system is designed to have secondary barrier/double-walled in the engine room.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
			Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	- There shall be vapour detectors installed in the engine room - The methanol supply system is designed to have secondary barrier in the engine room. - There should be a fire suppression system in the engine room. - There should be chemical powder fire extinguisher in the engine room.	B - Ex. Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low			
	What if there are environmental factors? - Sea Conditions - Vibrations - High temperatures - Icing / freezing - Lightning	High vibrations from the engine, resulting in premature failure of the piping system	leakage result in a create toxic atmosphere.	Design standards shall be followed to mitigate against excessive vibrations	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
			Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	- There shall be vapour detectors installed in the engine room - The methanol supply system is designed to have secondary barrier in the engine room. - There should be a fire suppression system in the engine room. - There should be chemical powder fire extinguisher in the engine room.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
		Icing or freezing of the tank vents	Overpressure methanol tank.	- No risks with icing of vents, as there is no experience of freezing on existing pilot boats- Tank should be able to stand some pressure.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	4. The tank vent should have a goose neck to prevent icing.		ScandINAOS / Simrishamn
	What if there is an electrical failure? What if there is a loss of ships power?	Loss of electrical supply to the outer tank ventilation fans	Loss of a layer of protection, in the event there was a methanol leak	- Methanol is not expected in the outer tank in normal operation - Vapour detector can detect if there is leakage without ventilation - All equipment are Ex-class	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
		Total ship black-out	Loss of visibility of the state of the systems and loss of methanol safety critical systems	It is likely that any interruption to the electrical supply would be affecting the whole electrical system and therefore result in the solenoid valves (FTC), returning to a safe position. (And back to diesel mode.)	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	5. Consider UPS feed for methanol safety critical systems (PLC, vapour monitor and sensors). 6. To have system to ensure the methanol supply is close in case of emergency.		ScandINAOS
	What if there is a failure in the control system / HMI / Communication systems?	Failure of the control and monitoring systems	Loss of visibility of the state of the systems and loss of methanol safety critical systems	- It is likely that any interruption to the electrical supply would be affecting the whole electrical system and therefore result in the solenoid valves (FTC), returning to a safe position. (And back to diesel mode.) - The PLC is marine certified.	C - Very Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	7. Procedure to be developed to ensure gas-free environment.		ScandINAOS / SMA
	What if there is a failure of the fire / vapour detection system?	Failure of a vapour detector in the engine room	Loss of safety critical systems	- There are two vapour detectors in the engine room - There is an additional portable vapour detector onboard.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
		Failure of a vapour detector in outer tank	Loss of safety critical systems	- There is extraction ventilation in the inter barrier space with a continuous ventilation @ 30AC/hr. It is designed to maintain the space at an under pressure to the rudder room, to prevent any external leakages. There is detection to monitor the differential pressures. - Crew is not expected to be present near outer tank except during maintenance. During maintenance, the portable vapour detector should be carried.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	What if there is a failure with the fire suppression system?	Failure of the fire suppression system for engine room	Loss of safety critical systems	- It has been confirmed that operational measures shall be implemented, to take the ship out of operation in the event of loss of the fire suppression system. - There is portable fire extinguisher onboard.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
		Failure of the fire suppression system for outer tank	Loss of safety critical systems	- It has been confirmed that operational measures shall be implemented, to take the ship out of operation in the event of loss of the fire suppression system. - There is portable fire extinguisher onboard.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
	What if there is an operational issue? - Start-up / Shut-down of systems / Changeover of Systems Over pressurisation event	An over pressurisation event in the supply system	Damage to methanol systems	The supply pump is protected by a pressure indicator. High pressure should shutdown the system.	D - Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			
	What if there is a loss of a 'safety critical system'	This arrangement differs from conventional arrangements with no N2 blanketing within the methanol tank.	This system could be exposed to an increased risk of a fire / explosion event. Although it is also understood that N2 systems to pose a risk of asphyxiation in the event of persons entering confined spaces, where N2 has displaced the breathable air	There is a flame arrestor in the tank ventilation system, so no ignition source can get into the tank.	A - Remote	3 - Major	Low			
Bunkering	What if there is a leak? What if there is a hose failure? Differential	A leak at the methanol bunkering connection. For example due to o-ring aging.	Methanol leak from the connection and create toxic atmosphere.	- The connection coupling is a drip-free design, although it is noted that this is not designed to be a breakaway coupling.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	8. Crew doing bunkering should wear proper PPE during bunkering.		SMA

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	movement / dropped object		Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	- There is a coaming around the bunker connection, a leak would be visually detected and the pump stop.	B - Ex. Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low	9. Bunkering will only be completed when the weather / wave conditions permit it to be completed safely (i.e. with very little ship motion)		SMA
		Pin-hole leak in the bunkering hose	Methanol leak from the connection and create toxic atmosphere/impact to environment.	- It was considered that a pinhole leak would be visually identified and the pumps stop. - Methanol is consider low harm to marine life.	C - Very Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	10. Crew should visually check the bunkering hose prior bunkering.		SMA
			Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	It was considered that a pinhole leak would be visually identified and the pumps stop.	C - Very Unlikely	2 - Localised	Low			
		Rapture of the bunkering hose	Methanol leak, with an increased risk of a fire event	It was considered that a rapture would be visually identified and the pumps stop.	B - Ex. Unlikely	3 - Major	Medium	11. The pressure of shore bunker station should be as low as possible.		SMA
	What if confusing methanol and diesel bunkering?	Connect methanol bunker hose to diesel tanks.	Engine stop. Methanol in non-hazardous area.	- Bunker connection for diesel has a different size than methanol.	A - Remote	1 - Minor	Low			
	What if the system is overfilled?	Overfilling of the tank during the bunkering process	Overfilling of the methanol storage tank during the bunkering process, could result in a significant release of methanol through the tank vent system and pose a fire risk.	- A bunkering procedure shall be in place between the supplier and the ship. - The methanol tank has a high level (visual and audible) alarm and a high-high level that automatic shutdown pump through SSL. - There should be no one onboard during bunkering according to bunker procedure.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low	12. The tank ventilation outlet should be pointed away from the space occupied by crew. (e.g. door)		ScandiNAOS / Simrishamn
	What if the system is overpressurised? Vent releases?	The system overpressurised during the bunkering process	Damage to the methanol storage or piping systems, resulting in a significant methanol leak.	- The tank is naturally ventilated; it would no restriction in the vent line. - The tank level indicator is a pressure type that will gives high alarm if overpressure. - A rapture of the system can be detected by the vapour alarm in outer tank.	B - Ex. Unlikely	1 - Minor	Low			

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	What if there is a static discharge?	A potential difference between the bunkering arrangement and the ship	There could be a static discharge, which could create an ignition source in the event of a leak of methanol	- A bunkering procedure shall be in place between the supplier and the ship	A - Remote	1 - Minor	Low	13. The bunker hose / bunker station to comply with static discharge requirements.		SMA
Usage - Engine	(Engine should be approved in a separate process)									
General Operation & Emergency Scenarios	Human Factors Are there any issues with the understanding / operational of the system including alarms and suitable actions / responses to them? Or unintended operation? What if persons do not have sufficient training, competence, expertise?	No reasonably foreseeable risks were identified, the system is considered to be similar to existing technology.		- The control and monitoring system will ensure that it operates safely.- There will be monitoring on the bridge.- Familiarity training shall be provided for the systems and understanding of alarms as well as the general hazards associated with methanol.- The vessel always has the diesel fuel system as a backup.				14. SMA to provide training to concerned people.		SMA
	What if inspection / maintenance routines need to be completed on the methanol systems? What if safe access is not provided?	No reasonably foreseeable risks were identified, operation and maintenance procedures are to be developed as part of the project.		- The PLC should prepare to warn a failed sensor.- SMA have a procedure to maintain the system.				15. Conditions for methanol pumps running / valves opening are both: 1. Engine running 2. No critical alarm		ScandINAOS
	What if 'hot' works need to be completed onboard?	No reasonably foreseeable risks were identified, this would be covered under the ships existing safe systems of work / safety management systems and permit to work systems								
	What if someone smoking onboard?	Smoking onboard	Possible source of ignition					16. There should be a "No smoking" sign onboard		Simrishamn

PROMPT	GUIDANCE	CAUSES	CONSEQUENCES	SAFEGUARD	Risk			RECOMMENDATIONS	COMMENTS	RESPONSIBILITY
					L	C	RR			
	What if there are other risks (Confined Space Entry, Working at Height, Working over Water)?	Persons entering confined spaces where there has been a methanol leak	Methanol is toxic by inhalation or ingestion (LTEL - 200 ppm), with a number of adverse health issues during over-exposure or prolonged exposure. In addition, it can produce toxic effects via skin absorption (with the eyes being particularly sensitive). In high concentrations it has a detectable odour, however, it can go undetected by humans in low concentrations.	- Familiarity training shall be provided for the systems and understanding of alarms as well as the general hazards associated with methanol.- There should be a portable methanol vapour detector in PPM level onboard.						
		Tool drop	Possible source of ignition	- Heavy tools with suitable protection to prevent spark if dropped.						
	What if persons there is a spillage or persons are exposed to methanol?	Persons exposed to methanol, due to a spillage or leak scenario	Methanol is toxic by inhalation or ingestion (LTEL - 200 ppm), with a number of adverse health issues during over-exposure or prolonged exposure. In addition, it can produce toxic effects via skin absorption (with the eyes being particularly sensitive). In high concentrations it has a detectable odour, however, it can go undetected by humans in low concentrations.	- Familiarity training shall be provided for the systems and understanding of alarms as well as the general hazards associated with methanol.- There should be a portable methanol vapour detector in PPM level onboard.- Suitable PPE shall be worn if persons are working on methanol systems- Eye wash bottles shall be provided at all locations where methanol systems can be accessed.						